

VRIO Analysis in the Commercialization of the Traditional Music Industry

Hartana Erlangga¹, Sonny Rustiadi²

^{1,2}School of Business Management, Institut Teknologi Bandung

ABSTRACT: Art is one of the elements of human culture in general which is an expression of the creativity of the culture itself. Culture-based creativity is a reflection or uniqueness of a nation's identity. However, in the current era of globalization, traditional arts are increasingly being abandoned by the public. Based on the data released by jabarprov.go.id about West Java arts' status state that there are several traditional arts that are almost extinct and there will be an increasing number of traditional arts that follow extinction. One of the reasons is that the current generation is more interested in popular music than traditional music or in other words they are not sufficiently concerned about their own culture. This is also because many think that traditional art is outdated. Not only experiencing extinction, several Indonesian traditional arts have also been claimed by other countries. Quoting from kompas.com (2010) in his article entitled "Angklung Will Become a World Cultural Heritage" which also discussed where angklung as a traditional art from Indonesia was claimed by another country which infuriated the Indonesian people, and after the debate between Indonesia and Malaysia. Angklung then was registered as an Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH) of Indonesia at UNESCO in November 2010. In order to actively participate in preserving and maintaining the existence of angklung in society, RagamLaras came up with an innovation for angklung, where the RagamLaras angklung has 15 scales that can play both pentatonic and diatonic notes in one angklung ensemble. It is hoped that it can provide a new presentation for the performing arts of angklung and open space for creativity for traditional artists, as well as spreading the public awareness, especially the younger generation, to get to know and preserve the nation's culture better.

KEYWORDS: Angklung, Awareness, Culture, Innovation, RagamLaras, Traditional music.

INTRODUCTION

Culture is a way of life that is developed and owned by a group of people that is developed and passed on from generation to generation. Culture is an important element forming the identity of a large group of people, especially a nation. The personality of a nation will be reflected through its culture. Universally, culture has several elements which include several things in it such as customs, morals, beliefs and art. However, in the current era of globalization, traditional arts are increasingly being abandoned by the public. This is in line with the data below which shows the number of arts that are almost extinct. In the present or in the future, the responsibility to develop and preserve this ancestral heritage is no longer fully determined by the government, but by the community, in this case they are artists, art lovers, art workers and art observers and others so that the arts and culture not lost or destroyed in the swallow of time. Especially now, foreign culture and modernization are the daily consumption of young people. Not only experiencing extinction, but several Indonesian traditional arts have also been claimed by other countries. Angklung as a typical Sundanese instrument is not only the pride of West Java, but has now become an instrument of pride for the Indonesian people. This is demonstrated by the recognition of the Angklung as an Intangible Cultural Heritage by UNESCO. However, this should not necessarily make the Indonesian citizen only proud and then remain silent. Because the inauguration of the angklung as an Intangible World Cultural Heritage belonging to Indonesia must still be maintained and preserved for the next generation.

Departing from concerns about the extinction of traditional arts due to being eroded by foreign cultures that are more easily accepted by young people in line with current conditions where there is no interest in traditional arts. Because of these concerns, RagamLaras is here with the aim of growing people's interest and re-interest in traditional arts. The innovations and developments carried out by RagamLaras regarding the addition of a number of new scales that have never been offered by other providers in the traditional musical instrument industry, can be a new thing to be introduced to the wider community, especially the younger generation to be more interested in traditional music. Currently, to be able to foster public interest in traditional art, an approach to direct consumers must be taken, so that the traditional music performed by RagamLaras is familiar and popular in the community. The approach taken is not only from musical compositions but also from new scales and also traditional musical instruments, namely the RagamLaras angklung.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Lawrence, in his book entitled Go To Market Strategy says that "Go-To Market Strategy is a game plan to reach and serve the right consumers in the right markets, through the right channels, with the right products and provide the right value proposition.". This is in line with what was said by Zoltners, in his book entitled Sales Force Design For Strategic Advantage which says that "Go-To-Market more broadly refers to how companies serve customers with a combination of Sales, Financing, Logistics, Services". Choosing the best go-to-market strategy is an important endeavor for both companies and new products because it creates the difference between companies that will survive and succeed from those that will not achieve success in the business environment. The best approach for companies to enter the market is to examine and understand what their customers need before making a decision to enter the market (Ashkenas & Finn, 2016). This is also in line with what Pauceanu said in her book entitled Innovation, Innovators and Business which said "The go-to-market strategy helps companies to achieve success in the business environment through an approach that enhances the company's ability to meet the needs and expectations of consumers from the start", from this it can be stated that a go-to-market strategy can and is important to implement to launch a product. According to Entzminger (2020), VRIO considers that it is through the firm's internal organization that resources are transformed into competitive advantage. The resource based view (RBV) focuses on specific resources and highlights that competitive advantage is based on valuable, rare, inimitable resources and organization (VRIO)".

III. METHODOLOGY

In this study a qualitative method will be carried out with the aim that the data obtained will be more in-depth from relevant respondents according to research needs. Qualitative research methods are considered important to be used in this research to find out how important it is to innovate in the traditional music industry and to find out the market potential as well as the commercial value for the RagamLaras angklung. In terms of data collection method, in this study primary and secondary data will be used. Primary data was obtained through in-depth interviews conducted by researchers with experts and consumers to find out about the external company. This research will use in-depth interviews with experts, interviews with several consumers and do external observation to collect data. In this qualitative method, to analyze the data from the interviews, narrative analysis will be carried out with the aim of understanding in depth the answers from the interviews given by the respondents to the questions asked and the ongoing discussion. After conducting narrative analysis which aims to find out statements from respondents regarding RagamLaras from an internal and external perspective which were analyzed using the narrative analysis method, the researcher also conducted a literature study to analyze secondary data. After collecting and analyzing the data the researcher applied the results of the analysis to a framework, namely VRIO.

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULT

Regarding VRIO to consider that it is through the firm's internal organization that resources are transformed into competitive advantage. The resource based view (RBV) focuses on specific resources and highlights that competitive advantage is based on valuable, rare, inimitable resources and organization (VRIO). Researchers conduct a VRIO analysis to find out the tangible and intangible resources owned by the company to determine the company's competitive advantage that can be used to differentiate from others and to enter the market. The table below is a list of resources and capabilities owned by RagamLaras based on the results of interviews and observations conducted with the owners and creators of RagamLaras.

Figure 1. VRIO Framework Process, Entzminger (2020)

Table 1. VRIO Analysis of RagamLaras

Resources & Capabilities	Valuable	Rare	Inimitable	Organized	Implications
Innovate 15 music scales	✓	✓	✓	✓	Sustained Competitive Advantage
Already have Copyright for the RagamLaras Scales	✓	✓	✓	✓	Sustained Competitive Advantage
Combining Traditional and Modern music	✓	✓			Temporary Competitive Advantage
Combining Traditional and Modern Instrument	✓	✓			Temporary Competitive Advantage
Introduce traditional cultural art and music broadly	✓	✓			Temporary Competitive Advantage
Angklung with 15 music scales which can played any genre (both traditional and modern)	✓	✓	✓	✓	Sustained Competitive Advantage
Entertain people through new kind of music	✓				Competitive Parity

(source: Erlangga, 07 February 2023)

From the results of the analysis carried out and applied to the VRIO framework above, it can be seen that RagamLaras has three factors that can help RagamLaras to be successful in achieving a ‘Sustainable Competitive Advantage’, including: Innovate 15 music scales, already have copyright for the RagamLaras’ scales, and angklung with 15 music scales which can plays any genre (both traditional and modern). From the results of data processing using the VRIO tools, it can be concluded that RagamLaras has something that can be used as a ‘Sustainable Competitive Advantage’ which is useful for entering the market.

V. CONCLUSION

Angklung as a typical Sundanese instrument is not only the pride of West Java, but has now become an instrument of pride for the Indonesian people. This is demonstrated by the recognition of the Angklung as an Intangible Cultural Heritage by UNESCO. However, this should not necessarily make the Indonesian citizen only proud and then remain silent. Because the inauguration of the angklung as an Intangible World Cultural Heritage belonging to Indonesia must still be maintained and preserved for the next generation. Departing from concerns about the extinction of traditional arts due to being eroded by foreign cultures that are more easily accepted by young people in line with current conditions where there is no interest in traditional arts. Because of these concerns, RagamLaras is here with the aim of growing people's interest and re-interest in traditional arts. In order to actively participate in preserving and maintaining the existence of angklung in society, RagamLaras came up with an innovation for angklung, where the RagamLaras angklung has 15 scales that can play both pentatonic and diatonic notes in one angklung ensemble. It is hoped that it can provide a new presentation for the performing arts of angklung and open space for creativity for traditional artists, as well as spreading the public awareness, especially the younger generation, to get to know and preserve the nation's culture better.

VRIO analysis used to analyse the company’s competitive advantage potential in the industry. From the result, RagamLaras has three factors that can help the company itself to be successful in achieving a ‘Sustainable Competitive Advantage’, including: Innovate 15 music scales, already have copyright for the RagamLaras’ scales, and angklung with 15 music scales which can plays any genre (both traditional and modern). From the results of data processing using the VRIO tools, it can be concluded that RagamLaras has something that can be used as a ‘Sustainable Competitive Advantage’ which is useful for entering the market.

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